

RELIGIOUS EDUCATION IN AZERBAIJAN: DEVELOPMENT OF RELIGIOUS EDUCATION FROM PAST TO PRESENT

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ABSTRACT

In this article, the development of religious education in Azerbaijan will be discussed in general terms and the process from the past to the present will be summarized. Azerbaijan, whose history goes back to ancient times, has witnessed many events. Different religions took place in the religious history of Azerbaijan, and Islam and the Islamic religion initiated a radical change in the region. Religious education in Azerbaijan is provided both as an elective course in public schools and more comprehensively through private religious schools and departments in universities. As for religious education, we can emphasize that with the spread of Islam in Azerbaijan, religious education activities were formed at the same time. In this study, religious education in Azerbaijan and the historical development of religious education are analyzed. The history and current development of religious education in Azerbaijan has passed through important stages depending on the history of the country and social changes

Keywords: Religion, religious education, Azerbaijan, state, Islamic religion.

INTRODUCTION

Located at the junction of Europe and Asia, Azerbaijan has been a place where people of different religions and cultures have lived since ancient times. Representatives of different religions who took refuge in Azerbaijan after being persecuted and tortured in different parts of the world have always lived here in peace, mutual understanding and tranquility. A number of religious educational institutions related to Zoroastrianism, Judaism and Christianity operated in pre-Islamic Azerbaijan. After the spread of Islam in Azerbaijani lands, a new phase was entered in this field and educational institutions teaching Islamic sciences began to operate. As in many Muslim countries, the establishment of religious education and religious education institutions in Azerbaijan coincides with the early periods when Islam spread in this region. This is due to the high value Islam places on science and knowledge [15, p. 166]. Azerbaijan has taken the necessary measures for the revival of religious life since the 1990s after independence. The Azerbaijani government has made the first attempts to provide proper religious education to people and to create feelings that can respect the values of the national state. The Azerbaijani state sent its own people to Muslim countries such as Libya, Turkey, Saudi Arabia, Egypt, Syria and Pakistan for educational purposes. In 1992, an agreement was made with the Presidency of Religious Affairs of Türkiye to open the Faculty of Theology under the auspices of Baku State University [16, p. 67]. Baku Islamic Madrasa, which started operating in 1989, was enlarged and turned into a University in 1992. Because the Theology faculties of Kafkaz University and Azerbaijan International Universities exist and have been turned into an important part of these universities. In 1993, one of the biggest works in the field of religious education in Azerbaijan was the opening of doctoral education in the Theory and History of Religion at the Manuscripts Institute of the Azerbaijan Academy of Sciences. In addition, Quran courses have started to operate in many cities and villages of Azerbaijan. Other activities in this

field include the National Faculties of Ethics and Islam at Shamakhi and Shaki Pedagogical Schools, Aliabad Islamic Madrasa, Shaki Islamic Sciences and Hafez Madrasa, Khosrow Islamic Madrasa, Baku Shabnam Madrasa, Rasul-Akram Madrasa, Imam Hussein Madrasa. In our research, the spread of Islam in Azerbaijan, religious education of children, as well as organizations providing professional religious education were examined. We will discuss how religious education is provided in Azerbaijan, organizations providing religious education, the number of students receiving religious education and its effects on employment. The population of the research consists of all madrasahs providing religious education in Azerbaijan, universities with faculties of theology, students and teachers studying in madrasahs and faculties.

MATERIALS AND DISCUSSION

Different sects in Azerbaijan from Past to Present

Although there are different religions and beliefs in Azerbaijan, not even one of them has lasted as long as Islam. If we pay attention to history, we can see that the history of Christianity, which was widespread in these places before Islam, included only the northern parts of Azerbaijan and, in other words, the areas of Albania in the Balkan geography. The first facilities where Islamic education was given in Albania were masjids, imam houses and similar places. In the first 4 and 5 centuries of Islam, even though there were no legal institutions that could provide much Islamic teaching, communities discovered different methods. The religious education of the Muslim community in Albania following communism can be evaluated in two stages: The first stage covers the period between 1991 and 2002, and the second covers the period from 2002 to the present. In both times, the merits of religious teaching and the situation of the Muslim community produced various results. For this reason, it is necessary to reveal and explain these features in order to understand today's current situation very well. Only in this form can religious education in Albania be fully

appreciated. Belief in fire, which emerged before Christianity, was widespread in the south of Azerbaijan - in the lands of Atropatena [11, p. 93]. When viewed from this perspective, we can say that Islam is the traditional religion that has maintained its leading position in Azerbaijan for the last 14 centuries. For this reason, it is very important for this religion to become widespread in Azerbaijan and to know its history of transformation into a national religion and to pass it on to future descendants in terms of keeping our traditional and spiritual virtues alive. Unfortunately, sometimes there are even those who argue that Islam is accepted through its brute force. However, such baseless empty defenses have no basis either in science or history [15, p. 172]. Because Azerbaijanis are not a nation that changes religion by force, nor is Islam considered a religion that justifies this difficulty. On the other hand, the truths in the historical sources also prove that the protests and marches that leaked the reluctance of the society in the period when the religion of Islam became widespread in Azerbaijan were not for this religion, but against the occupation policy of the Arabs. Because it is necessary to consider that if Islam had been accepted by the power of the sword, its progress in Azerbaijan would not have been so permanent and it would not have been a traditional religion. On the contrary, history shows that the expansion of Islam within the Turkish communities, including the Azerbaijani community, was a situation of enormous historical significance. By accepting this religion, Turkish nations accepted the principles of a broader and richer culture and had an important role in the emergence, progress, strengthening and protection of this culture [7, p. 57].

The first home of the ancient Albanians is today's Azerbaijan. Old Albania was separated by the Caspian Sea in the east, the Kur river in the southwest, the Kanik (Alazan) river in the northwest, the Kurin, Tabasaran tombs and the Caucasian mountain range from Kazikumik and Kaytak. Archaeological and toponymic studies carried out in today's Azerbaijan have revealed the Old Albanian culture in its entirety as ashes. It is seen that the Alban and Atropaten tribes living in Azerbaijan migrated to the Balkans after the attacks of the tribes coming from the southern Caucasus. The state founded by the Atropatenes dominated the region after the Battle of Gavgamel in 331 BC. Later, when the South Caucasian tribes took control of the district, the local people descended to the Balkans via the Black Sea, as before, and the Azeri Albans in Albania and Macedonia named the region where they settled as Albania. The similarity of the Albans to the Scythians in Azeri sources is expressed in the following words: "Plutarch describes the Albans as a brave people. Strabo says about the Albans: "They differ with their beauty and height". Herodotus, the "Father of History", talks about the war between the Persian King Darius and the Scythians. As a result, he records that they settled in the district called (Scythia Minor) between the Carpathian Mountains and Dobrudja and gave their name to this district, and that they made great progress and gave the works of a superior culture. In another source, he gives the following information on this

subject. It talks about Arrania and Albania, two places that gave rise to Azerbaijan in the IV and III centuries BC. Various languages are spoken in this satrapy, which came under the rule of the Persians over time. When we research the history of Albania, it cannot be a coincidence that the Albania (Albania) government was established on the coasts of Macedonia and Dalmatia in the 1st century BC, and the Albanians who migrated to Macedonia in Azeri history established the Albania (Albania) government in the 1st century BC. During this period, moderate Shiism began to spread in Azerbaijan and reached Darban. Sunni Hanafi and Shiite imam schools became the leading schools. At the same time, Sufism was also gaining strength. The fact that the khanate on the Pirsaat River in Shirvan was established at that time is an indication of this. During the formation of the great Seljuk State, the social organization we mentioned within the sectarian structure was very confrontational and very noisy. It is important that during the time of Togrul Khan, he controlled a large geography from Transoxiana to Baghdad and that there was a movement of various religions and interpretations accumulated in the old customs of these places. However, the social base shaped by migrations and raids reveals the main pillars of the confusion we are talking about. When fiqh schools are researched in the geography of "Khorasan and Transoxiana" during the formation of the huge Seljuk State, it is seen that two sects came into conflict. Among these sects, Hanafism is more common. Indeed, when Seljuk Bey became a Muslim in Jand, he chose Hanafism as his sect. Therefore, the Seljuk khanate was generally affiliated with the Hanafi sect. Another fiqh sect that was as widespread as Hanafis during the time of Togrul Khan is known as Shafi'ism. As it turns out, the main center of spread of the Shafi'i sect was Egypt. By the time of Tuğrul Bey, the Shafi'i sect had serious supporters, although they were not as common as the Hanafis, in the cities of Khorasan and Iraq. The situation of the political-theological sects following the dissolution of the Seljuks is also of great interest. Ash'arism, which emerged in the line of Bakillanî (d.403/1013)-İbn Fûrek (d.406/1015), focuses on the Küllâbî tradition and has a thought described in a way that includes all hadith scholars except the Hanbalis. Based on the validity of its content, Ash'arism at this time is named in the sense of "Theological Ash'arism". During the founding period of the Seljuks, Ash'arism entered a phase of change and philosophization that emerged with Juwayni (d. 478/1085), one of the most prominent scientific figures of his time. Although, in the geography of "Khorasan" and "Transoxiana", the Shafi'i-Ash'ari community had the most common name after the Hanafi sect. Shiite sects also had a certain influence in the mentioned age. The Imamiyya sect has a respectable population in limited areas of Iraqi territory, Qom primarily in Iranian cities; Rey had a relatively small community in Khorasan cities such as Nishapur. The Ismaili sect is in a very strong place due to the influence of the Fatimid State. During the time of Tuğrul Khan, the western policy of the government was determined by the Fatimids and their imperialist sectarian policies. It is seen that before the Seljuks,

Fatimid dais were engaged in publishing in Khorasan and Transoxiana. Among the Shiite followers, the only sect that the Seljuks did not face as a problem was Zaydism. The decreasing trend of the Zaydis, who had supporters in Khorasan cities such as Daylam, Rey and Qom in the lands of Tabaristan during the time of Togrul Khan, continued for a long time in this age. In the fourth phase of the Seljuk period (mid-XI century - mid-XIII century), Sunnis became stronger in the region, the position of Shiism weakened, and the Shafi'i sect became the leading sect. The fifth phase covers the period of Mongol campaigns (first half of XIII century - second half of XV century). Hurufism began to gain strength during this period. Its founder Fazlullah Naimi, Ebulhasan Aliyyul-Ala and poet Nasimi were the most influential representatives of Hurufism. Seyyid Yahya Shirvani Bakuvi, the second leader of the Halvatiye sect, was one of the most famous people of that period [16, p. 75]. The sixth phase concerns the reign of the Safavids (1501-1786) and the Ottomans (1281-1924) from the century onwards. Safavids preached Shiism and wore an imam with 12 red stripes on their heads in honor of the 12 Shiite imams. That's why they were called "golden heads". After the Battle of Chaldiran, supporters of the Sunni Hanafi sect began to increase in Azerbaijan. The next stage of Islamization in Azerbaijan covers the period after the occupation of the country by the Russian Empire [14, p. 190]. 2 Muslim administrative institutions were created in the South Caucasus - the Sunni Spiritual Administration (Mufti), headed by the mufti, and the Shiite Spiritual Administration (Sheikh-Islam), headed by the Sheikh. During the existence of the Azerbaijan Democratic Republic (1918-1920s), the religious affairs of the Muslims of the South Caucasus were carried out by these two departments. After the establishment of the Soviet power in Azerbaijan in 1920, the institution of sheikhdom was abolished, Muslim clergy were persecuted, and most of the mosques were closed [16, p. 83].

The Situation of Religious Education During the Soviet Administration

We observe that after the establishment of the Soviet power in Azerbaijan, all subjects related to religion were removed from school programs and the teaching-learning process was based on the ideology of atheism [5, p. 321]. Of course, at the initial stage, measures of a reformist nature were not unambiguously welcomed by the population. Parents did not send their children to school, but tried to give them religious lessons at home. However, as a result of the harsh and irreversible policy initiated by the Bolshevik regime in the 30s of the last century, such attempts were decisively blocked and a 70-year period of "atheism" was established in all educational institutions in the country. After the establishment of the Soviet power in Azerbaijan, from the 1920s of XX century onwards, as a result of the abolition of sharia education, clergy and madrasah teachers were subjected to pressure, and religious education in Azerbaijan weakened for 70 years [13, p. 115]. After the years of repression, especially in the years when the USSR ceased to exist - near its collapse, centers of religious education were

established in Bukhara (Uzbekistan), Samarkand (Uzbekistan), Kazan (Tatarstan) and other cities of the Union. The Muslim population of the USSR, including Azeris, went to these centers to learn religious sciences [6, p. 125]. Starting from XII century, Islam took shape in Azerbaijan and began to develop more rapidly. This phase is called the "golden age" of Azerbaijani culture. The most important feature of this level was that scholastic religious sciences, as well as Arabic grammar, medicine, astrology, Eastern languages, literature, logic and other subjects were taught in the madrasas operating next to mosques at that time. In XII-XV centuries, many madrasahs were operating in Tabriz and Baku, including "Kazaniyye", "Falakiyya", "Sheikh Kemaleddin Hocandi", "Damascus", "Gazi Sheikh Ali" and others in Tabriz; The educational centers of Seyyed Yahya near the "Shah Mosque" of the Palace of the Shirvanshahs in Baku and Sheikh Safi in Ardabil were quite famous [16, p. 98]. The university in Rabi-Rashidi, located in the northeast of Tabriz, was considered the largest educational institution in the Near and Middle East. In schools and madrasahs operating in mosques and households, all administrative and pedagogical activities were carried out mainly by clergy. State institutions, as a rule, did not provide any assistance to educational institutions. Schools and madrasahs were supported by donations from the families of the children studying there, from the state, or by income from the extracurricular activities of the clergy. Nadir Shah, who came to power in 1776, deprived the schools of their last source of income, the foundation lands. The khans, who later seized real power in these places, refused to return these lands to their real owners - religious communities and school madrasahs. It is possible to mention the name of Shamakhi's "Malham" madrasah among the first schools established in Azerbaijan. The founder of this famous scientific institution was the uncle of the Azerbaijani poet Kaghani Shirvani, the influential figure of the period, Dr. Kafiyyeddin Ömer [8, p. 13].

Religious Education in Azerbaijan during the Years of Independence

An institution that provides higher religious education in Azerbaijan is Baku State University Faculty of Theology, which has been operating since 1992. "(For according to moral education, Islamic Quran plan, studying the types of Hadith, types of Quran, religious philosophy, dogmatic theology, Islamic basics of Islamic history, basics of interpretation, basics of Muslim rights, Islamic rights Commentary, basic principles of Islamic history, Islamic scriptures, Islamic principles such as Arabic, Holy Quran plan geography of countries, religious history, logistics, education, 'philosophy of Islam, sophistry, psychology of religion, religious sociology of Islamic subjects, method pedagogues, history of Islamic culture, history of physical education, general linguistics of Azerbaijan, English, Persian, Turkish, Arabic, religious music, medicine "The Department of Islamic Sciences and Languages, which operated within the faculty until it was incorporated into the Azerbaijan Institute of Theology, trained theologians, Arabic teachers and translators in their fields [7, p. 86].

Since the beginning of the five-year education faculty's operations, qualified faculty members on religious subjects have been sent here by the Religious Foundation of the Republic of Turkey; foreign languages and other humanitarian subjects were taught by local experts [14, p. 186]. In recent years, all subjects have been taught by local experts [17, p. 386]. To date, 870 graduates have graduated from the faculty. Since its establishment, approximately 25 graduates of the faculty have been sent to Turkey to continue their education at master's and doctoral levels. Approximately 10 students completed their education and returned to Azerbaijan to continue their activities as teachers at the Faculty of Theology. One academician, six theology and five philology doctors served in the faculty teaching staff [12, p. 189]. One academician, six doctors of theology and five doctors of philosophy in philology serve in the faculty teaching staff. Baku State University - Faculty of Theology (Baku State University Faculty of Theology is a bridge of brotherhood established between Turkey and Azerbaijan.) In addition to religious subjects, Azerbaijani history, sociology of religions, philosophy of religions, history of religions, psychology of religion, logic, informatics, geography of Islamic countries. , general Arabic linguistics, civil defense, English, Arabic, Persian and Turkish languages were given. The total number of courses taught at the faculty was 25 [15, p. 173] There is no religious education in primary, secondary and high schools in Azerbaijan). By the Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Mr. Ilham Aliyev, dated February 9, 2018, a new educational institution - Azerbaijan Theological Institute was established in Azerbaijan and Baku State University Faculty of Theology (Faculty of Theology) was established in the 1992/93 academic year by the Ministry of Education of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Baku State University and the Turkish Religious Foundation. It was established in accordance with the agreement signed between the faculty. Now the duration of education at the faculty is five years. Graduates of the faculty are given two specializations - theologian / Islamic scientist and Arabic teacher. So far, 8 graduates have defended their doctoral thesis in the field of theology and received the degree of doctor of theology. In the first academic year (The first number of students admitted to the faculty (1992-1993) was 61. More than 600 students have been accepted to the faculty so far.) In a sense, this decision was to reduce Azerbaijan's foreign dependency in religious education, to meet the need for local theologians and perhaps to create the country's religious education center in the long term. In any case, this was a new step, the Azerbaijani state officially established and sponsored a religious educational institution. By the way, education at the Theological Institute is free, all expenses are covered by the state, namely the State Committee on Work with Religious Institutions and the Fund for the Propagation of Spiritual Values operating under it [3]. The establishment of the Azerbaijan Theological Institute is one of the most serious and important decisions taken in the religious history of Azerbaijan. In 2018, admission to the Azerbaijan

Theological Institute was carried out in two fields: Islamic Sciences and Religious Sciences. Clergy will be trained in the field of Islamic Sciences and theologians in the field of Religious Sciences. Currently, 109 students are studying at undergraduate and graduate levels at the university. In the Theological University, 1 faculty – Theology; There are 3 departments - Languages and social issues, Religious sciences, Islamic sciences [1, p. 22]. Core Values of Azerbaijan Theological University Transparency is a value that the AIE team prioritizes in all areas of cooperation. AIE believes that transparency will increase efficiency. Impartiality is a value that shows that AIE will cooperate with every institution and society within the framework of the laws of the Republic of Azerbaijan. AIE is ready to cooperate with every religious sect to protect values and establish peace. A sense of social responsibility is a value that AIE adopts and instills in its faculty, students and staff. In addition to actively participating in social projects, AIE is ready to cooperate with secondary and higher education institutions in religious and psychological fields. High academic quality is a priority value adopted by AIE in the field of teaching, learning and research. The Institute has prepared the curriculum and course schedules of the courses taught in accordance with contemporary education standards. Tolerance and multiculturalism are among the values that the Theology collective primarily adopts in every field. AIE accepts religious and ethnic diversity as an important value. The Institute is ready to cooperate within the framework of law with all sects that contribute to world peace and security [12, p. 197]. Religious Education in Legislation: Article 18 of the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan states that religion is separate from the state and all religious beliefs are equal before the law [9, 2012]. Moreover, in the second paragraph of this article, it is prohibited to spread and promote religions (religious movements) that degrade human dignity or contradict humanitarian principles, and finally, in the third paragraph, it is stated that the state's education system has a secular character [12, p. 189]. At the same time, Article 10 of the Law on Freedom of Religious Belief states that religious education institutions may establish religious centers and departments solely for the training of religious officials and other personnel in religious specialties. It is noted that religious educational institutions operate on the basis of special approval granted by the relevant executive authority.

The collapse of the Soviet empire was the beginning of an important historical process in the life of the Azerbaijani people, as well as in the life of many nations, politically. The study of all aspects of cultural heritage was encouraged. There have been radical changes in the field of culture. The forbidden religious literature of that period fell from the dusty shelves and was presented to the understanding of today's youth. In the historical past of the people, importance was given to supreme values such as religion in terms of their contribution to the construction of a strong state and a strong society. Religious education in Azerbaijan went through more complex stages after the years of

independence. After Azerbaijan gained its independence, new religious education institutions were established in the country and the attention and care of the state was covered. Azerbaijan Theological Institute is one of the newly established religious educational institutions. The establishment of the Azerbaijan Theological Institute is one of the most serious decisions taken in the history of religions in Azerbaijan. The Institute faces big tasks. One of the important issues is the training of Islamic scholars and religious scholars who have deep religious and worldly knowledge, are intelligent, broad-minded, and have various foreign language skills [2].

Some work has already been done in this direction. Examining foreign experience in order to obtain high results, experience (in general, the spiritual experiences that man experiences in front of the Being that he accepts as the creator or sacred, proving the existence of the Creator based on different emotions such as encountering the Creator, uniting, destroying the thought in Him) shopping is of particular importance. For this purpose, the educational programs of Muslim and non-Muslim countries, especially the world-famous Oxford and Cambridge Universities, are examined and collaborations are made with various world universities. It is difficult to imagine the spirituality and lifestyle of the Azerbaijani people without Islamic values.

CONCLUSION

It is an undeniable historical fact that the religion of Islam plays an exceptional, unifying and progressive role in the destiny of Azerbaijan and its people. Islam, which left deep traces in the genetic memory of the people, had a strong impact on the formation of Azerbaijanis as a single nation, on the formation of their national identity, statehood tradition and culture [4]. In addition to belonging to the Islamic civilization, the people of Azerbaijan experience the importance of being universal, civilized, resistant to coercion in religion, acceptable and multi-civilizational [10]. In this respect, Azerbaijan, which has chosen the path of democratic, legal and secular state building and is taking firm steps towards the establishment of civil society, stands out in the Islamic world. Because Azerbaijan, which plays the role of a bridge between Eastern and Western cultures, makes significant contributions to the advancement of dialogue between religions and cultures in the world, to the establishment of peace and harmony on earth, and sets an example and a unique way of living together. Tolerance and tolerance show that Azerbaijan remains committed to both universal and national moral principles, within the scope of the great spiritual and moral laws of Islam, which has shown progressive activity in its historical past.

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